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APPROACHES TO THE LEGAL REGULATION OF SUKUK. A COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF THE LEGAL REGULATION OF SUKUK ISSUANCE IN INDONESIA, MALAYSIA, AND THE UNITED KINGDOM

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ANNOTATION

The Sukuk structure is very similar to bonds among financial securities. Many jurisdictions have chosen to apply the rules used for bonds to Sukuk as the most appropriate legal solution to allow the issuance of Sukuk. However, proper legal and regulatory standards are essential to distinguish Sukuk from bonds. This article aims to compare the legal and regulatory frameworks established for the issuance of Sukuk in various countries and to study the main rules that facilitate Sukuk issuance. The article is based on a comparative approach that analyzes the legal and regulatory approaches that support Sukuk issuance in certain countries. Some of the information mentioned in this article has been gathered from relevant laws and regulations of countries like Indonesia, Malaysia, and the United Kingdom, as well as from legal literature and academic articles. The research results show that Sukuk regulation can be implemented in two ways: first, by enacting a separate law, and second, by making amendments to the existing legislation. International experience shows that, in cases where regulating Sukuk at the same level as traditional bonds is necessary to permit its issuance, it is essential to refer to pre-developed and applicable models. This provides best practices for implementing the regulatory framework of Sukuk by some jurisdictions, helping to strengthen local regulations and enhance the position of Sukuk in the market.

Keywords: Islamic finance, Islamic bank, sukuk, musharakah, mudarabah, bonds, Islamic financial services, trust investment certificates, derivatives, securitization.

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**SUKUKNI HUQUQIY JIHATDAN TARTIBGA SOLISHDAGI YONASHUVLAR.
INDONEZIYA, MALAYZIYA VA BUYUK BRITANIYADA SUKUK EMISSIYASINI
HUQUQIY TARTIBGA SOLISHNING QIYOSIY TAHLILI**

ANNOTATSIYA

Sukuk tuzilmasi qimmatli qog'ozlar ichida obligatsiyalarga juda yaqin tuzilishga ega. Ko'pgina yurisdiksiyalar Sukuk chiqarishga ruxsat berish uchun obligatsiyalarga nisbatan qo'llaniladigan qoidalarni Sukukka qo'llashni eng maqbul huquqiy echim sifatida tanlagan. Biroq, Sukukni obligatsiyalardan ajratib turish uchun to'g'ri huquqiy va tartibga soluvchi me'yorlar muhim ahamiyatga ega. Ushbu maqola turli mamlakatlarda Sukuk chiqarish uchun belgilangan huquqiy va tartibga soluvchi doiralarni taqqoslash va Sukuk chiqarishni osonlashtiradigan asosiy qoidalarni o'rganishga qaratilgan. Maqola ayrim mamlakatlarda Sukuk chiqarishni ta'minlaydigan huquqiy va tartibga soluvchi yondashuvlarni tahlil qiluvchi taqqoslash usuliga asoslangan. Ushbu maqolda keltirib o'tilgan ayrim ma'lumotlar Indoneziya, Malayziya va Buyuk Britaniya kabi mamlakatlarning tegishli qonunlari va qoidalaridan, shuningdek, huquqiy adabiyotlar va ilmiy maqolalardan to'plangan. Tadqiqot natijalari Sukukni tartibga solish ikki yo'l bilan amalga oshirilishini ko'rsatadi. Birinchisi, alohida qonun qabul qilish va ikkinchisi esa amaldagi qonunchilikka o'zgartirishlar kiritish orqali. Xalqaro tajriba shuni ko'rsatadiki, sukukni chiqarishga ruxsat berish uchun uni an'anaviy obligatsiyalar darajasida tartibga solish zarur bo'lgan holatlarda oldindan ishlab chiqilgan va amal qilish mumkin bo'lgan modellarga murojaat etish zarur. Bu ba'zi yurisdiksiyalar tomonidan sukukning tartibga soluvchi doirasini amalga oshirish bo'yicha eng yaxshi tajribalarni berib, sukuk bozoridagi o'rnini mustahkamlash uchun mahalliy qoidalarning kuchaytirilishiga yordam beradi.

Kalit so'zlar: Islom moliyasi, islom banki, sukuk, mushoraka, muzoraba, obligatsiya, islom moliyaviy xizmatlari, ishonch investitsiya sertifikatlari, derivativlar, sekyutarizatsiya.

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**ПОДХОДЫ К ПРАВОВОМУ РЕГУЛИРОВАНИЮ СУКУК. СРАВНИТЕЛЬНЫЙ
АНАЛИЗ ПРАВОВОГО РЕГУЛИРОВАНИЯ ВЫПУСКА СУКУК В ИНДОНЕЗИИ,
МАЛАЙЗИИ И ВЕЛИКОБРИТАНИИ**

АННОТАЦИЯ

Структура сукук очень похожа на облигации среди финансовых ценных бумаг. Многие юрисдикции решили применять правила, используемые для облигаций, к сукук как наиболее подходящее правовое решение для разрешения выпуска сукук. Однако надлежащие правовые и нормативные стандарты имеют важное значение для того, чтобы отличить сукук от облигаций. Цель этой статьи — сравнить правовые и нормативные рамки, установленные для выпуска сукук в разных странах, и изучить основные правила, которые облегчают выпуск сукук. Статья основана на сравнительном подходе, который анализирует правовые и нормативные подходы, которые поддерживают выпуск сукук в определенных странах. Часть информации, упомянутой в этой статье, была собрана из соответствующих законов и нормативных актов таких стран, как Индонезия, Малайзия и Великобритания, а также из юридической литературы и научных статей. Результаты исследования показывают, что регулирование сукук может быть реализовано двумя способами: во-первых, путем принятия отдельного закона, и, во-вторых, путем внесения поправок в существующее законодательство. Международный опыт показывает, что в случаях, когда регулирование сукук на том же уровне, что и традиционные облигации, необходимо для разрешения его выпуска, необходимо ссылаться на заранее разработанные и применимые модели. Это обеспечивает наилучшую

практику внедрения нормативной базы сукук некоторыми юрисдикциями, помогая укрепить местные правила и повысить положение сукук на рынке.

Ключевые слова: исламские финансы, исламский банк, сукук, мушарака, мудараба, облигации, исламские финансовые услуги, трастовые инвестиционные сертификаты, деривативы, секьюритизация.

Introduction.

Sukuk has become one of the most widely used Islamic financial instruments in the Islamic capital market. According to a recent report on Sukuk, IIFM (International Islamic Financial Market) reported that global sukuk issuance in 2019 amounted to US\$145.70 billion. Such sukuk issuance has been observed in both minority and majority Muslim jurisdictions, by sovereigns and corporate entities, and has diversified its offerings to attract and offer non-traditional content. Although the structure of sukuk is closer to the capital market bond process, sukuk faces various legal challenges and this has led to the need for a legal framework. Examples of such problems include:

- the lack of a definition of sukuk in the current legislation, the inadequacy of company laws to create special purpose vehicles (SPVs);
- the lack of permission to separate the ownership of assets;
- the weakness of bankruptcy laws to protect the rights of sukuk holders;
- the absence of a Sharia supervisory board, and many other regulatory problems [1, p-15].

In particular, most discussions on sukuk have focused on the economic and financial benefits in the capital market, while the legal and regulatory frameworks of sukuk have been less discussed. However, interest in the legal and regulatory aspects of sukuk has increased significantly since the 2008 global financial crisis. As a result, the need for proper legal and regulatory frameworks has become increasingly important in both developed and developing jurisdictions, and the importance of distinguishing bonds from sukuk has become apparent.

Malaysia, US\$261 billion, Indonesia, US\$70 billion, and the UK, US\$364 million, were selected because they have actively pursued reforms to attract Islamic financial instruments, particularly Sukuk, and have developed laws and regulations that allow for the introduction of Islamic finance in their countries [2, p-26.]. Therefore, studying the sukuk regulatory framework in these jurisdictions may provide best practices for other countries that have not established their own sukuk regulatory frameworks.

Capital Market Regulatory Requirements.

As public and private entities become interested in accessing capital markets and seeking to leverage them as a source of finance, countries are increasingly interested in establishing a robust regulatory framework for their domestic capital markets. They need to have strong legal and regulatory frameworks for securities and institutions. Such frameworks have helped explain why developed countries have adopted strong capital market regulations, which focus on two areas:

The first is to find a legal framework and the second is to support capital market institutions. Therefore, an efficient and effective capital market is the result of well-developed legislation and a strong regulatory framework in place [3, p-33.].

With such a legal framework, successful capital market operations and issuances have enabled companies to raise funds and offer more securities to investors. This can increase legal protection and confidence in investing in domestic or foreign companies. In addition, policymakers can intervene from time to time through capital market regulators with necessary legal reforms to ensure a sound, clear and fair environment for all parties involved in the capital market. To this end, the International Organization of Securities Commissions (IOSCO) has introduced its objectives and principles for securities regulation. This is important in ensuring fair and efficient capital markets, protecting investors and trying to reduce systemic risks [4, p-35.].

Islamic capital market regulation.

Many countries are trying to introduce Islamic capital markets in their domestic markets to facilitate the process of Islamic instruments. IOSCO is also one of the institutions interested in the Islamic capital market and has published a special report titled “Islamic Capital Market Fact Sheet”.

It found that there is no need to add any special requirements to the existing capital market regulations and there is no need to register or allow Islamic Capital Market (ICM) products to be traded. However, it recommended the establishment of a Shariah-approved advisory board. The same legal and regulatory frameworks for conventional products have been applied to ICM products. However, some countries such as Malaysia have introduced a special regime for ICM. Thus, enabling legislation through effective laws, rules and procedures was needed to ensure the successful development of ICM in such jurisdictions. These key elements support the formation of a sound ICB to ensure the smooth functioning of capital market institutions. This enforces various laws and regulations that are binding on market participants [5, p-150-154.]. These capital market institutions have a clear process for adopting, implementing and amending existing laws and regulations within the market. Of course, by doing so, these institutions help facilitate the integration of the ICB segment into the existing capital market in many jurisdictions.

Summary of Sukuk.

As a widely used instrument of the Islamic Capital Market (ICM), sukuk has many definitions from the perspective of various international Islamic financial institutions. The most common definition is provided by the Accounting and Auditing Organization for Islamic Financial Institutions (AAOIFI). This institution defined sukuk in its Shariah Standard No. 17, entitled "Sukuk Investments", as follows:

“Sukuk are certificates of equal value representing unequal shares in specific assets, rights to use and services or assets of a specific project or specific investment activity, but this is after the redemption of the Sukuk, the closing of the subscription and the use of the proceeds for the purpose intended for the Sukuk issue [6, p-468.]”

This definition has been adopted by many entities and financial institutions. However, as described above, sukuk has some differences from bonds and stocks. Sukuk is similar to stocks in terms of ownership of the underlying assets and the distribution of profits and losses. It can also be compared to bonds in terms of the concept of debt, i.e., “I Owe You,” which requires a certain amount to be repaid when due. Sukuk is a more hybrid financial instrument, different from bonds or stocks.

Legal and regulatory framework for sukuk issuance.

A healthy sukuk market must be governed by a strong regulatory framework and have a sound Sharia supervisory board under the leadership of government institutions. Sukuk was initially considered by market experts to be similar to bonds, which led to its acceptance as a securitization process. Although Sukuk is Sharia-compliant, it is still classified according to the same procedures as conventional instruments. In this context, some rules may be applicable to Sukuk, while other rules require appropriate modifications to ensure proper understanding. Thus, the same legal and regulatory frameworks as for bonds in the capital market are applied to Sukuk. Many developed and developing country jurisdictions have developed laws and regulations to introduce Sukuk in their countries, which are intended to protect investors in Sukuk by providing better explanations.

It usually comes as a document passed by a government agency directly involved in securities or by a group of people organized under a legislative institution such as parliament. Sukuk legislation is considered to be the formal enactment of a specific Sukuk law or an amendment to existing laws in parliament. The legal framework for Sukuk can be defined as the definition of the powers and responsibilities of the entities authorized to raise funds, within a framework of clear and unambiguous rules.

Such a regulatory framework required the involvement of a specific government agency as a supervisory body to interpret existing laws and develop specific rules, guidelines, and guidelines to be followed by industry professionals. It typically comes with extensive and comprehensive details for implementing legislation on the issuance, registration, trading, and redemption of sukuk.

Sukuk regulatory approach.

Many jurisdictions have taken steps to introduce a legal or regulatory framework for Sukuk for the ICM (Islamic Capital Market) following the global financial crisis of 2008. The aim of having a legal or regulatory framework for Sukuk was to create a level playing field for all participants in the capital market compared to traditional financial instruments.

The absence of such a framework defeats its purpose and hinders the effective functioning and growth of the market. Therefore, the efforts of regulators are increasingly focused on identifying an adequate legal or regulatory framework that will address the issues related to sukuk and help achieve the objectives. In fact, the ICM (Islamic Capital Market) had a two-pronged approach to regulating sukuk: (a) enacting separate Sukuk laws or amending existing laws.

While many jurisdictions have expressed interest in adopting new and separate sukuk regulatory instruments, others have chosen to amend the current legal framework or use existing securitization legislation without creating new regulations. As a result, the choice of legislative route through parliament has been made in several countries according to local market conditions, or some countries have chosen a mixed approach, where traditional rules are adapted to obtain the legal opportunity for sukuk issuance.

Shariah control.

Another pillar of the regulatory framework is Sharia compliance. Some regulations require the establishment of a Sharia Supervisory Board under the supervision of the government's financial authority or include this board in the capital securities law or other regulations. However, despite its important role in supervising Islamic financial instruments, other jurisdictions have neglected the role of the Sharia Supervisory Board in overseeing and ensuring the Sharia compliance of instruments such as sukuk. The presence of a Sharia Supervisory Board provides greater confidence and peace of mind in making Sharia-compliant investments in sukuk. In addition, a sukuk sharia committee is recommended by the highest financial authority to ensure a reliable regulatory and adequate control system from the sukuk issuance stage to its redemption. The presence of a sharia committee increases investor confidence in sukuk issuances [7].

Sukuk is Sharia-compliant and fully backed by real, tangible assets, meaning that sukuk holders deal with real assets rather than the face value of the securities. The Sharia Committee is also mandated to organize sound management of the sukuk market and continuously monitor its compliance with Sharia [8, p-45].

Many countries are currently trying to establish a regulatory framework for sukuk. This framework requires strong legislation, appropriate authority for issuing sukuk, clear ownership rules between the originator and investors, sound Islamic contracts, and strong Sharia oversight. These and other elements should ensure that sukuk is introduced under adequate legal and regulatory frameworks that are appropriate for each jurisdiction.

Indonesia, Malaysia and the UK are leading the way in introducing new regulations allowing Sukuk issuance. Indonesia and Malaysia are seeing a strong need to diversify sources of funding to bolster government budgets and support public projects. Another reason is that sukuk is increasingly being used as a financial instrument instead of bonds around the world. This shows that bonds are not particularly strong in Muslim countries.

While many jurisdictions prefer to issue sukuk separately, others choose to gradually amend existing laws. The rationale is to simplify the process and encourage large-scale sukuk issuance. Countries such as Indonesia, Malaysia, and the United Kingdom are examples of jurisdictions that have chosen to move to a legal framework that allows for sukuk issuance.

Indonesia has struggled to establish a sufficient legal framework for sukuk issuance since its inception. The main obstacle has been the lack of clarity in the rules governing sukuk [9, p-126.]. This was particularly a direct result of various shortcomings in the Indonesian legal system. Legal issues were identified as major obstacles, including difficulties for the government and private corporations in assigning and transferring ownership of assets to other parties. There was also a lack of legal protections to protect the owners of the underlying assets in the event of the issuer or founders going bankrupt. Another issue is related to asset securitization, and the capital market regulatory authority, Badan Pengawas Pasar Modal (BAPEPAM), had issued Law No. IX.K.1 to regulate asset-linked securitization until 2011. However, this regulation has some shortcomings related to Islamic asset securitization, which has mainly been used as a legal basis for issuing sukuk only in the case of debt securitization.

In addition, the “Rent Law” established by Presidential Decree No. 61 of 1988 became an additional problem. The problem here was mainly related to Article 1533 of the Civil Code, which only regulated securities arising from debt relations. However, the lease payment and leased assets were not explained in a broad and clear manner. Also, the Decree of the Ministry of Finance No. Kep.Men.RI.No 1169/KMK.01/1991 on the Lease Procedures of 1991 contained some conditions that contradicted the principles of Sharia.

The fact that Indonesian law does not recognize sukuk as an instrument different from conventional bonds has created another problem for corporate issuers. Prior to 2008, under Indonesian law, sharia bonds were considered debt instruments, which was inconsistent with the sharia principles of sukuk. Therefore, the unclear rules on sukuk have negatively affected the issuance of this instrument among Indonesian issuers and investors.

Despite being the first European country to list sukuk on the London Stock Exchange (LSE), the UK has faced some legal hurdles.

The UK government has seen the development of a legal framework for the issuance of sovereign sukuk, as well as the introduction of tax exemptions as a first step in developing this market. The diversity of the underlying legal structures of sukuk has created complexities for UK regulators. For example, the difficulty of classifying them into the regulatory framework. In particular, sukuk are treated as traditional bonds under section 235 of the Sukuk FSMA 2000. If sukuk were to be issued as CIS, this would be a potential trap for sukuk issuers and would impose a higher regulatory burden than traditional securities issuers.

The issue raised here is that sukuk are treated as unregulated CIS units. In the first case, only UK professional investors have access, while in the second case, where the assets are located in the UK, sukuk issuers are treated as fiduciaries. Therefore, it was necessary to obtain FSA approval before attempting to issue sukuk. Such regulatory approvals and other tax burdens generally make sukuk and sukuk issuers less attractive in the UK than traditional debt securities issuers.

The Malaysian government has made the country a pioneer jurisdiction in adopting regulations for Islamic bonds, which were created in 1983 under the Government Investment Certificate (GIC), now known as the Government Investment Indenture (GII), which was a non-tradable, interest-free debt instrument. This issue prompted the regulator to use the Bai al-Inah as the underlying contract to enable secondary market trading. The concept of Bai al-Inah was implemented in the 1990s and 2000s to structure Islamic paper debt.

The main problem of this study is related to the differences of opinion between Islamic bankers and Sharia scholars, especially in transactions based on Bai al-Inah. This is because Bai al-Inah was one of the prohibited services in the Middle East. In addition, all Islamic Private Debt Securities (IPDS) were subject to conventional rules. Similar conventional rules were applied to Islamic securities in terms of disclosure and registration requirements, shareholder protection, and company law, which led to the consideration of effective legislation that would shape IPDS.

In general, the Indonesian approach is to allow the issuance of Sukuk without specific rules. However, this requires the application of traditional bond rules to the issuance of Sukuk. Similarly, the approach in Malaysia is to encourage the use of IPDS, but no legislation has been enacted. The Malaysian experience focuses on the conditions for using traditional securities rules for the issuance of IPDS. However, the UK government’s approach is to avoid the unregulated procedures for sukuk under FSMA 2000 when launching this instrument on the UK capital market [10, p-5].

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